

Beyond Schelling's Threshold: Quantifying Emotional Impetus of Human Residential Distribution Formation through Geo-tagged Facial Analysis

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Abstract:

The spatio-temporal distribution of human populations and its underlying drivers have been widely discussed in geographical research. However, current approaches often treat individuals as statistical units devoid of subjective states, neglecting the potential influence of emotional dispositions and cognitive perceptions on residential choices or migration behaviors. While some researchers have highlighted the role of subjective perceptions in shaping population distribution and human mobility—for example, Yi-Fu Tuan's emphasis on environmental perception as a guide to human actions and Schelling's segregation model based on homophily preferences—empirical validation of these theories remains limited due to a lack of suitable datasets. This limitation stems from the scarcity of datasets that concurrently document individuals' emotional states, sociodemographic attributes, and precise geo-locations.

To bridge this gap, we propose an innovative methodology that leverages geo-tagged Flickr photographs to obtain emotional expression records with high spatial and temporal resolution. Our framework utilizes advanced facial recognition technology to systematically detect human faces, and further identifies their demographic attributes and quantifies emotional expressions using deep-learning methods. Taking the United States as a case study, our research mainly focuses on three interrelated dimensions: (1) spatio-temporal trends in collective emotional expressions, (2) spatial patterns of population segregation and its temporal changes, and (3) potential associations between emotional states and migration dynamics.

Our preliminary findings reveal a nationwide decline in positive emotional expressions from 2004 to 2014, which coincided with a decrease in residential segregation on the macro scale. Notably, individuals residing among populations more similar to themselves appear to exhibit stronger positive emotional expressions, which provides empirical evidence for Schelling's theoretical predictions. This study establishes a replicable framework for investigating the complex interplay between human emotions, social dynamics, and spatial behaviors, while also pioneering the integration of emotional dimensions into research on residential patterns and human mobility.

Keywords: Emotional geography; residential distribution; collective emotion